

THE ROLE OF THEORETICAL ANALYSIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PLAY THERAPY.

Nematullaeva Sarvinoz Xushvaxt kizi

Termez State Pedagogical Institute, Teacher of psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074406>

Annotation: This article provides extensive information about the history of game theory in the development of play therapy and its place in the history of psychology.

Keywords: play therapy, child personality, mental development, psychotherapy, individual abilities, socialization, activity, mental development.

Play therapy became popular in the 1940s and 1950s. The use of the game for the purpose of psychotherapy is carried out within the framework of various theoretical schools and directions. Game techniques differ in the level of directiveness, the frequency of game sessions; the game can be used as a method of individual exposure and for the purposes of group psychotherapy. Sometimes children play with their parents. According to different authors, the psychotherapist can be given the passive role of an observer, the role of a partner, the role of a partner in a game or the role of a leader.

The development of ideas about children's games is a remarkable page in the history of psychology. The task of creating a new game theory set by L. S. Vygotsky is covered in detail in the works of the most prominent Russian psychologists A. N. Leontiev, A. V. Zaporozhets, D. B. Elkonin, P. Ya. Galperin, and in the researches of their employees and students. A detailed and complete presentation of the history of the creation of local game theory, its main concepts and experimental studies is presented in the fundamental monograph of D. B. Elkonin.

At the heart of the local theory of children's play is the idea of its social nature. Role-playing games arise as a result of a change in the child's place in the system of social relations in the course of historical development, in which, based on the development of society, the involvement of children in effective work is pushed back. "There is a new period in the child's development, which can rightfully be called the period of role-playing games," writes D. B. Elkonin (1978, p. 63).

A game is understood as "a special type of child's activity, which embodies the attitude to the surrounding, first of all, social reality, has its own content and structure - a special theme and motives of activity, and a special system of actions" (Elkonin, 1978), p. 150).

The imaginary situation, the role and the game actions that implement it are distinguished as the main structural divisions of the game. In a developed role-playing game, it is shown that the basis of the role is not objects, but relationships between people. Game activities are divided into components such as plot and content. The plot of the game is the sphere of reality that is repeated by children in the game. The content of play is repetition by the child as a central, characteristic moment of activities and relationships between adults.

Role-playing is not a productive activity, the motive of the game lies in its process. At the same time, the development of the motives of the game is visible in the change of content. In the early stages of childhood, the game motive realizes the need for actions with objects. Later, during the formation of the need to act like an adult and the selection of an adult as a role model, the motive becomes not game actions, but repetition of the role. In a developed game, it is the imaginary situation and role that becomes the central meaning-generating motive.

The analysis of changes in the content of the game allowed D. B. Elkonin to show the stages or levels of development of the role-playing game, which reflects the differences in obedience to the role rule. And finally, one of the most important rules of the internal theory of children's play is to approach play as a leading activity. This means that "in connection with the development of the game, the most important changes take place in the psyche of the child ... mental processes develop that prepare the child to move to a new, higher stage of his development" (Leontiev, 1972 , page 476).).

Not only new motives are formed in the game, but also their psychological form changes. The game creates conditions for the development of self-conscious behavior, the foundations of self-awareness are formed in the game. The game has the most important effect on the development of mental actions, prepares the transition to the formation of new intellectual operations, it is "a source of development and creates a zone of close development" (Vygotsky).

The study of gaming disorders is a holistic approach to the analysis of pathological phenomena. As D.B. Elkonin noted, "the game can be divided into a set of individual abilities: "perception + memory + thinking + imagination". "the qualitative specificity of the game is completely lost". Thus, studying the game disturbed by the disease, the pathopsychologist determines the disturbance of mental functions and emotional-affective states in their interaction. B. V. Zeigarnik notes that "a pathopsychological experiment should be a well-known model of a life situation that can actualize not only the patient's mental

operations, but also his attitude, direction". There is no doubt that the game experiment provides an opportunity to study such a life situation. Thus, childhood The study of mental disorders during the 19th century with the help of game activities corresponds to the basic principles of pathopsychological experiments. games even have some advantages over other methods of child pathopsychology. The fact is that such an approach allows not only to identify some features of the child's development that are different from the norm, but also, most importantly, to observe the ways of their formation. Disturbed under the influence of the disease, game activity leads to the appearance of special pathological neoplasms. Therefore, if the pathopsychologist sets himself the task of studying disorders in the general process of development and its internal mechanisms in the context of mental illness, the need to analyze the game arises.

"Conscious management of the mental development of the child is carried out, first of all, by controlling his basic, leading attitude to reality, controlling his leading activity ... it is necessary to learn how to manage the game" (Leontiev, 1965, p. 247) .

Friedrich Schiller writes: "People play only when they are human in the full sense of the word, and when they play, they become fully human." In psychotherapy with children and adolescents, play is considered a silver bullet, that is, an excellent way to help children who are under psychological stress to stabilize emotionally, begin healthy development, and overcome traumatic experiences. Play is their language, they communicate with them and find new solutions through them.

In conclusion, we must say that the role of play theories in the development of play therapy is incomparable. Because today, in our developing country, conducting play therapy with a child who is developing as a person makes a significant contribution to his physical and mental development. It should be emphasized that play therapy can be used not only with children with developmental disabilities, but also with healthy developing children.

Использованная литература:

1. A.S. Spivakovskaya; Psixoterapiya: o'yin, bolalik, oila. 2012-y
2. Неъматуллаева, С. (2020). Психология детей в возрасте 5-7 лет. Студенческий вестник, (5-1), 62-63.
3. Ne'Matullayeva, S. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA O 'YIN TERAPIYASINI QO'LLASHGA OID QARASHLAR. Science and innovation, 1(B4), 444-449.

4. Nematullaeva, S. (2023). DEVELOPING COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH GAME THERAPY. *Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence*, 2(4), 86-88.
5. Ne'matullayeva, S. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida oyin terapiyasini qo'llashda innovatsion usullar. O 'zbekiston milliy universiteti xabarlari, 1(6).
6. Nematullaeva, S. (2023, April). The role of play therapy in a child's life. In *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 9-10).
7. Неъматуллаева, С. Х. (2023). Влияние Игровой Терапии В Формировании Личности Детей. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 4(2), 31-33.
8. Kizi, N. S. K. (2022). Use of Game Therapy in Preschool Educational Organizations.
9. Нематуллаева, С. (2023). Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning shaxs sifatida kamolotida o'yin terapiyasining ahamiyati . *Современные тенденции психологической службы в системе образования: теория и практика*, 1(1), 43-46. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/psychological-service-education/article/view/23475>
10. qizi Ne'matullayeva, S. X., & Ulug'bek qizi Abduqahhorova, M. (2023). BOLA SHAXSINING RIVOJIDA O 'YIN TERAPIYASINI QO 'LLASH SHART-SHAROITLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 341-344.